

Chemiluminescence of 2-(3-Phthalhydrazidylazo)-1,3-diketones

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Three phthalhydrazidylazo- β -diketones have been synthesised and characterised as the corresponding hydrazones on the basis of ir and nmr spectral evidences. All the three compounds showed more intense chemiluminescence than 3-aminophthalhydrazide (luminol). Greater rigidity through stronger hydrogen bonding and more extensive conjugation through hydrazone structure seem responsible for the enhanced chemiluminescence observed. Emitting species in the chemiluminescent reaction of the compounds have been identified as the corresponding phthalic acids.

SINCE Albrecht¹ first described the bright chemiluminescence (C. L.) of luminol (3-aminophthalhydrazide), C.L. of organic cyclic hydrazides has received increasing attention²⁻⁴. Although many compounds, particularly substituted-phthalhydrazides, have been examined, only a very few have surpassed luminol in efficiency. From results of our studies on ligand properties of novel heterocyclic azo compounds^{5,6}, we here report the synthesis, characterisation and chemiluminescence behaviour of the title compounds; the 1,3-diketones used being acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane.

Experimental

Luminol was prepared and purified as reported before^{7,8}. The azo compounds were prepared as follows. To a stirred suspension of luminol (0.88 g, 5 mmol) in 6 M HCl (3 ml), kept cold below 5° in an ice-salt bath, was added dropwise an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.35 g in 1 ml). The cold mixture was stirred for 1 h and then filtered quickly from any unreacted luminol, to yield the diazonium chloride solution. The filtrate (after destroying excess nitrous acid in it with urea) was added slowly to a stirred solution of β -diketone (5 mmol) in aqueous ethanol (10 ml, 70% v/v). Sodium acetate was added to maintain pH of the mixture at 7-8. After continued stirring for 1 h, the precipitated yellow dye was filtered, washed repeatedly with water, sucked dry and recrystallised twice from hot ethanol to yield chromatographically pure (tlc/silica gel) material. 3-[(2,3-Dihydro-1,4-phthalazinedione)yl-5-azo]-2,4-pentanedione (phthalhydrazidylazoacetylacetone) (1) (90%), m.p. 312° (Found: C, 55.23; H, 4.39; N, 19.08. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4N_4$ calcd. for: C, 55.57; H, 4.98; N, 19.44%).

2-[(2,3-Dihydro-1,4-phthalazinedione)yl-5-azo]-1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (phthalhydrazidylazobenzoylacetone) (2) (82%), m.p. 275° (Found: C, 61.16; H, 4.30; N, 15.63. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4N_4$ calcd. for: C, 61.71; H, 4.31; N, 16.00%). 2-[(2,3-Dihydro-1,4-phthalazinedione)yl-5-azo]-1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (phthalhydrazidylazodibenzoylmethane) (3) (68%), m.p. 280° (Found: C, 66.39; H, 3.81; N, 12.96. $C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_4$ calcd. for: C, 66.99; H, 3.88; N, 13.39%).

A Beckmann DU 2 uv-vis spectrophotometer, a Perkin-Elmer 257 ir spectrophotometer, a Varian XL-100 nmr spectrometer and a Aminco Bowman spectrophotofluorimeter fitted with a IP 21 PM tube and xenon excitation source were used. Ir spectra of the compounds were recorded in nujol mull and also in KBr disc. ¹H nmr spectra were taken in DMSO-d₆. Chemiluminescence spectra were obtained using the spectrophotofluorimeter, after turning off the excitation source. The following procedure was employed for C.L. measurements. To a solution of the azo compound (1 ml, 10⁻³ M) in aqueous NaOH or ethanolic NaOH (10⁻³ M) taken in quartz cell was added H₂O₂ (0.025 ml, 10⁻³ M) from a syringe (in such a way as to ensure thorough mixing of the reactants) and the spectrum recorded quickly (200 nm min⁻¹). For comparison, C.L. spectrum of luminol was also recorded under identical condition. All fluorescence measurements were carried out using 10⁻³ M solutions with an excitation wavelength of 350 nm. The instrument was calibrated using quinine sulphate.

Results and Discussion

Diazonium salts react readily with β -diketones to yield monohydrazones⁹⁻¹¹, and since 3-aminophthalhydrazide exists as mono-enol^{5,9,12}, the

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION AND EMISSION BAND MAXIMA (nm) OF PHTHALHYDRAZIDYLAZO- β -DIKETONES

Compd. no.	Longest wavelength uv band in methanol	Fluorescence		C.L.*	Fluorescence	
		in 0.01 M HCl	in 0.01 M NaOH		after C.L.	of corresponding phthalic acid
Luminol	355	425	—	425 (1.00)	425	425
1	390	440	450	475 (5.00)	430	475
2	395	470	500	510 (3.60)	430	505
3	410	480	500	480 (2.20)	430	480

* Relative intensities in parenthesis.

phthalhydrazidylazo- β -diketones can be represented as in structure below. This structure is quite in agreement with the ir and ^1H nmr spectral data of the compounds.

- 1, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$
- 2, $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
- 3, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

Infrared spectra of **1** show in the region $1700-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ three strong bands at $1670, 1650$ and 1625 cm^{-1} , and two medium intensity bands at 1615 and 1605 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1670 and 1625 cm^{-1} can be assigned to stretching of free acetyl carbonyl and hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl, respectively^{11,13}. The band at 1615 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the hydrazone form¹⁰, and the remaining two bands at 1650 and 1605 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and cyclic $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching, respectively, of the phthalhydrazide moiety^{6,12}. Spectra of **2** and **3** show band for free benzoyl carbonyl at $\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bands assignable to hydrogen bonded acetyl and benzoyl carbonyl, respectively, of **2** and **3** are observed at 1625 and 1618 cm^{-1} , respectively. As should be expected for the hydrogen bonded hydrazone structure, a strong and considerably broad band is observed at $3500-2400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the three compounds.

Absence of $=\text{C}-\text{H}$ proton signal of the β -diketonate moiety and presence of low field broad signal at $\delta 14$ in the ^1H nmr spectra of all the three compounds indicate that the compounds exist in the hydrogen bonded hydrazone form^{10,11}. In agreement with the structure proposed, spectra of **1** showed two methyl signals at $\delta 2.30$ and 2.65 .

Azo compounds are generally incapable of fluorescence, which on the other hand is almost

characteristic of compounds having hydrazone structure¹⁴. The three azo compounds show fluorescence in aqueous alkali and acid (Table 1).

The C.L. reaction of phthalhydrazides in alkaline medium is oxidative in nature and the corresponding carboxylates are the light emitters. The intensity of the C.L. emissions depends on the nature of the oxidising agent. In the case of luminol, intense emission is observed only when H_2O_2 and another oxidising agent, like hexacyanoferrate(III), persulphate *etc.* are used. However, in the case of the three azo compounds, H_2O_2 alone produces highly intense emission. The C.L. emission of the three azo compounds in aqueous alkali (using H_2O_2 as oxidant) has been compared with that of luminol under the same condition (Table 1). The C.L. maxima of the three azo compounds in aqueous alkali showed gradual shift to shorter wavelengths. The final wavelength in all the three cases was identical (430 nm) indicating that the final product after C.L. in all the three cases is the same. For the entire shift in wavelength, only about 15 min were required in the case of **1**, while in the case of **2** and **3**, 2.5 and 5 h, respectively, were required. Unlike in the case of luminol, the C.L. emission maxima and fluorescence maxima of the spent reaction mixture after C.L. are quite different (Table 1). The C.L. wavelength of these compounds matched well with the fluorescence wavelength of the corresponding phthalic acid (synthesised by coupling diazotised 3-aminophthalic acid with the β -diketones). Therefore, it can be concluded that the corresponding phthalic acids are the light emitters. Since the final wavelength of emission of the azo compounds is the same, and is close to the C.L. wavelength of simple 3-substituted-phthalhydrazides, it appears that the $\text{N}-\text{N}$ bond of the hydrazones is cleaved hydrolytically during the C.L. reaction, yielding simple 3-substituted-phthalhydrazides.

Intensity of C.L. emission in the case of the azo compounds is much higher than that of luminol, and the emission maxima occur at longer wavelengths. It has been reported in the case of substituted luminols, that departure from planarity leads to decrease in intensity of C.L. emission, and

also to a shift to shorter wavelength¹⁵. Cyclic hydrazides having extended conjugation and more planar arrangement are far superior in C.L. efficiency than luminol¹⁶. Thus, the observed increase in intensity and the red-shift in C.L. emission of these compounds can be attributed to increased planarity due to intra-molecular hydrogen bonding, and to increased resonance interaction from extended conjugation of the hydrazone form.

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